

THE CONCEPT OF AN INTERNATIONAL CONSTRUCTION CONTRACT

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***Annotation.** This article delves into the intricacies of international construction contracts, examining their legal frameworks, key elements, and practical implications. It explores the necessity of such contracts in the context of globalization and the increasing frequency of cross-border construction projects. The article outlines the standard forms used in international construction contracts, scientific opinions of some civilists regarding this matter.*

***Key words:** construction projects, construction contract, foreign element, purchase of goods, legally binding, final result, legal framework, local regulations, Choice of Law.*

The number of construction projects in Uzbekistan has grown significantly in recent years. Along with local contractors, the construction market of the country is enriched with new foreign participants. This, in turn, creates the need to regulate the construction legal relationship with a foreign element. To date, neither the legislation of our country or other countries, nor the international community has formulated the concept of an international construction contract. Moreover, the absence of conventional regulation of international construction contract creates the ground for the study of established customs to find out the sources of regulation of such relations. In this chapter we will study the opinions of scholars on the concept of international construction contract and the main points of legal regulation of this type of contract.

International construction is a phenomenon that appeared recently, but it has become widespread and developed due to the process of globalisation. Despite the development of this type of construction, the doctrine and laws do not formulate the concept of an international construction contract. Moreover, there is no single act that would regulate international construction relations. In this regard, the main source of regulation of this type of relations is an international construction contract concluded between the parties. In this regard, there is a need to formulate the concept of this type of contract. The Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 21.12.1995 (hereinafter - the Civil Code of the RUz) says that "an agreement of two or several persons on the establishment, change or termination of civil rights and obligations is recognised as a contract". In addition to this, domestic scientist H.R. Rakhmankulov distinguishes the following meanings of the contract:

- "as a legal relationship. It establishes, changes or terminates civil rights and obligations of the participants;
- As a legal fact giving rise to obligations. Conclusion of an agreement gives rise to civil legal relations;
- as a document fixing the fact of the emergence of an obligation by the will of its participants".

So what is a construction contract? "A construction contract is a contract for the sale and purchase of goods, works and labour for a fixed single price, payable in instalments as the goods are delivered and the work is performed" .

According to domestic legislation, more precisely Article 666 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "under a construction contract the contractor undertakes to build a certain object or perform other construction work on the customer's assignment within the period established by the contract, and the customer undertakes to create the necessary conditions for the contractor to perform the work, accept it and pay the agreed price". Professor H.R. Rakhmankulov emphasises that a construction contract is the basis for the emergence of not one, but several obligations. Also the author of comments to the

Civil Code of the RUz states that the construction contract can be singled out as a separate type of construction contract due to its distinctive features.

As to the subject of the construction contract, H.R. Rakhmankulov refers to the subject of the construction contract as the final result of the contractor's activity, therefore, under the construction contract it is the construction object delivered by the contractor to the customer. Within the framework of such subject of construction contract it is important to mention the direction of "complex" subject of construction contract, according to which the subject of the contract consists of two elements: the performance of work and the result of completed work.

V.R. Faizulin believes that "the subject of the construction contract consists in the performance of construction works by the contractor of construction or other works related to the object under construction and their transfer to the customer in the form of the final result".

Professor T. Randolph says that "a contract is a legally binding agreement between two or more parties to exchange something of value. In construction, this is usually money in exchange for construction services to build a project. A contract provides both contractual and legal obligations for both parties that are difficult or impossible to change".

As we noted earlier, in foreign and domestic legal doctrine, scientists have not been able to develop a definition of the international construction contract. In general, it should be recognised that the issue of defining the concept of international construction contract is poorly covered in legal science. We can say that an international construction contract should be understood as a construction contract complicated by a foreign element. But is it so?

According to V.A. Kanashevsky, "a construction contract may be qualified as an international contract if one of two conditions is present: commercial enterprises of the parties to such a contract - the contractor and the customer - must be located in the territory of different states or the contract works must be carried

out in the territory of another state, even if the parties have their commercial enterprises in the territory of one state". For example, in the UN Convention on Contracts for the International Sale of Goods, the criterion of internationality is commercial enterprises located in different States. Or Article 1 of the Hague Principles (Principles on Choice of Law in International Commercial Contracts of 19.03.2015) "a commercial contract is international except where the enterprises of each party are located in the same State and the relationship between the parties and all other relevant elements, irrespective of the law chosen, is related only to that State" .

Summarising the above, it can be seen that foreign authors describe the construction contract a little more broadly. In foreign literature construction contract is a set of services and works rendered by the contractor, the result of which is the final constructed object, while in domestic literature and legislation construction contract is only construction or capital repair of a building in exchange for a certain value. We can say that an international construction contract should be understood as a construction contract complicated by a foreign element.

Thus, in our opinion, a construction contract acquires an international character only due to the presence of a certain foreign element (subject or object), while the substance of the contract remains unchanged. It should be noted that neither the Uzbek legislation, nor the legislation of the CIS countries or the legislation of European countries defines the content of an international construction contract. In this regard, there is a problem of legal qualification by courts in resolving disputes arising from construction contract relations and related private law relations.

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